

SELF-ESTEEM AS A PREDICTOR OF ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

Self Esteem is a compelling element among students which can affect their academic performance. The higher level self-esteem will increase performance of students in their academics. The main aim of the present study was to find out the effect of Self Esteem on academic achievement of university students. On the basis of gender, locality, semester and program; differences between groups were observed. By using cross-sectional survey method, researcher conveniently sampled 160 students from University of Sargodha. An adapted questionnaire Rosenberg Self Esteem scale was used for data collection. The study was quantitative in nature. Data were analyzed through descriptive statistics frequency, mean, Standard Deviation and inferential Statistical test independent sample t-test, Analysis of Variance and Linear regression by using SPSS. Findings of the current study showed that students' Self Esteem has statistically insignificant effect on their academic achievement. It was also reported that Self Esteem was found the same among male-female and urban-rural university students. Also, the students at all levels (semesters) and in all programs were reported to have equivalent level of Self Esteem. It is recommended that a larger and more diversified sample would have yielded more robust results thus a reliable picture of the outcome.

INTRODUCTION

Self Esteem refers to a person's beliefs regarding their own worth and value; Self Esteem is significant because it is deeply influencing decisions of people. In other words, Self Esteem provides a motivational purpose by making it more or less possible that people will take care of themselves and look at their full potential. To some extent Self Esteem is a theoretical concept; it's tough for someone to understand who doesn't know it (Morelli, n.d). Self-esteem reflects the relationship between one's self-image and ones ideal self-image, representing an individual's sense of satisfaction with oneself. Self-esteem is regarded as the most significant psychological expression, making it a gauge of self-assessment. Additionally, there are two distinct sorts of self-

esteem: global and specialized. While academic self-esteem is more related to behavior and provides an indicators for academic success, global self-esteem is mainly related to psychological aspects (Ahmadi, 2020). Self Esteem can influence behavior and beliefs. It changes your views about how you feel and how you value yourself. It can change our thinking, confidence and self-image. What we mostly need is directly associated to our Self Esteem. On contrary, failure is more possible when we have low Self Esteem; because we will consider others when they tell us why we cannot succeed (Baumeister et al., 2003). Academic achievement affects a learner Self Esteem, inspiration, and purpose in higher education. Low educational performance decrease admission opportunities for students

seeking higher education. On the whole, academic achievement is the performance of every time that concludes Grade Point Average (GPA). Thus the GPA attained is the result of students' performance in tests, course work and examinations (Jayanthi et al., 2014). Academic achievement showed performance results demonstrate how much someone have achieved particular objectives that are the midpoint of behavior in instructional settings, especially in school, college, and university. Such accomplishment must be measured to a comprehensive construct to contain many areas of knowledge (Steinmayr, 2014). Such abilities are important in helping students to perform well academically (Iksan et al., 2011).

It was evident that university academic performance of students was significantly positively deterministic in relation to their sense of self-esteem. Numerous findings in the study literature support the beneficial effects of students' self-esteem on their academic performance, particularly at the university level. However, it is always affirmative to assume that some researchers in other places would have contested these findings.

A scientific theory's standing is constantly enhanced by such challenges. Karl Poppers' falsification theory is an important approach to accept such challenging results. His theory of falsification states that a theory is not scientific until it can be refuted. It is no longer a scientific theory if it cannot be refuted. In this work, we will not delve further into the notion of falsifiability. Our goal was to simply prepare the readers and researchers to comprehend the very difficult research findings.

Objectives of the Study

Following were the objectives of the study:

1. Find out the effect of Self Esteem on academic achievement
2. Compare the Self Esteem of male and female university student
3. Compare the Self Esteem of urban and rural university student
4. Find the difference in the Self Esteem of students at different semester
5. Find the difference in the Self Esteem of students of different programs

Research Hypothesis

Following were the hypothesis of the study:

1. H₁: There was no statistically significant difference in the Self Esteem of male and female students.
2. H₂: There was no statistically significant difference in the Self Esteem of urban and rural students.
3. H₃: There was no statistically significant difference in the Self Esteem of students at different semesters.
4. H₄: There was no statistically significant difference in the Self Esteem of students of different programs.
5. H₅: There was no statistically significant effect of Self Esteem on academic achievement.

Methodology

This section addressed methodology of the study. According to Rajasekar et al. (2017), research methodology is defined as the "procedures through which researchers set out regarding to their effort of describing, explanation and prediction of problem. The study was descriptive in nature. By using quantitative research method, cross-sectional survey strategy was used. In this design, the researcher administers a survey through an adapted questionnaire to a small group of people to recognize the tendency in attitude, views, behaviors, or else attributes of a large gathering of people (Creswell, 2012). The population of the study includes all the student of BS, BEd, MA, and MPhil program from all the sub campuses including main campus of the University of Sargodha. All the students at the main campus of the University of Sargodha were the accessible population. The sample includes male and female students of the University of Sargodha. By using, Convenience sampling technique, the researcher collected data from 160 students of different departments of the University of Sargodha. The research instrument used in this study was adapted questionnaires, Rosenberg Self Esteem Scale. The Rosenberg Self Esteem Scale, a generally utilized instrument based on self-report for assessing person's Self Esteem, was accessible on the following URL: http://fetzer.org/sites/default/files/images/stories/pdf/selfmeasures/Self_Measures_for_Self

Esteem_ROSENBERG_SELF ESTEEM.pdf (Rosenberg, 1989); and was permitted to be used freely. Pilot testing was conducted to calculate the internal consistency of the questionnaire. To determine the reliability, the data were analyzed by SPSS. The reliability of the data was found to be .600. Data were analyzed through descriptive (frequency, mean, and Standard Deviation) and inferential Statistical tests ; independent sample t-test, Analysis of Variance and Linear regression by using SPSS. Independent sample t-test was used to understand the variations in mean score of gender and locality of the university students; One way ANOVA was used to find out the differences among students of different semesters of various programs. Regression was used to estimate the effect of Self Esteem

(Predictor) on academic achievement which was an outcome variable. Researcher used following equation of linear regression:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta X + \epsilon$$

Y represents academic achievement, α represents intercept, β is the coefficient of X which represents Self-esteem, and the value of β denote the effect size of the predictor on the academic achievement.

Results

The evaluation and interpretation of the data were reported in this section. Main purpose of this study was to determine how self-esteem of university students affected their academic performance. Both descriptive and inferential statistics are used in the study in this section. a

Table 1 : Gender Wise distribution of the Sample

Gender	Frequency %
Male	59 (36.9)
Female	90 (56.2)
Not Mentioned	11 (6.9)
Total	160 (100)

In the descriptive section of statistical self-esteem, the sample's explanation is covered, and in the inferential section, the hypothesis is tested and the implications are explained. The responses' frequencies and percentages were noted as follows.

Table 1 revealed that there were 90 female students and 59 male students among the total responses. Of those who responded, 37% were men and 56% were women.

Table 2 : Locality Wise distribution of the Sample

Locality	Frequency %
Urban	96 (60)
Rural	64 (40)
Total	160 (100)

Table 2 showed that of the 160 students enrolled in the institution, 64 were from rural areas and 96 were from urban areas. Overall,

40.0% of students were from rural areas, while 60.0% of students were from urban areas.

Table 3: Semester wise distribution of Sample

Semester	Frequency	Percentage
1	03	01.9
2	76	47.5
4	43	26.9
5	01	00.6
6	24	15.0
8	12	8.1

Total	160	100.0
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Table 3 indicated that out of 160 university students, 3 (1.9%) were from the first semester, 76 (47.5%) from the second, 43 (26.7%) from the fourth, 1 (0.6%) from the fifth, 24 (15.0%) from the sixth, and 13 (8.1%) from the eighth semester of their studies.

Table 4: Program wise distribution of Sample

Program	Frequency	Percentage
BS	75	46.9
Masters	71	44.4
BEd	04	2.5
MPhil	10	6.2
Total	160	100.0

Table 4 showed that out of 160 university students, table 4 indicated that 75 (46.7%) were enrolled in a bachelor's program, 71 (44.4%) were enrolled in a master's program, 4 (2.5%), and 10 (6.2%) were enrolled in an MPhil program.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistic of the Sample

Self Esteem	Mean	SD
1. I have ability to manage, guide, facilitate a group or activity so as to maximize its success and the contribution of participants	2.10	0.80
2. I feel that I have number of good qualities	2.10	0.90
3. All in all, I am inclined to feel that I am a failure	3.60	0.50
4. I am able to do things as well as most other people	2.10	0.90
5. I feel I do not have much to be proud of.	2.70	1.20
6. I take a positive attitude toward myself.	2.00	0.90
7. On the whole, I am satisfied with myself.	1.90	0.80
8. I wish I could have more respect for myself.	2.00	1.00
9. I certainly feel useless at times	2.90	1.10
10. At times I think I am no good at all	3.00	1.20

Mean and standard deviation were shown in Table 5. The mean scores ranged from 1.90 to 3.60, presenting moderate levels of self-esteem among students. Standard deviation values showed reasonable variability in responses across items.

Table 6: Gender wise Difference

Gender	N	Mean	SD	SE Mean	t	p
Male	59	22.575	4.564	.5942	1.223	.189
Female	90	21.71	3.986	.4200		

In Table 6 the value of $t = 1.223$ and significant difference $p = .189$ explained that there was insignificant difference and therefore the null hypothesis: "There was no statistically significant difference in the Self Esteem of male and female students" was failed to be rejected. Male and female students had comparable level of Self Esteem.

Table 7: Locality wise difference

Gender	N	Mean	SD	SE Mean	t	p
Urban	96	22.625	4.88	.4987	1.311	.467
Rural	64	21.640	4.27	.5343		

In Table 7, the value of $t = 1.311$ and significant difference $p = .467$ illustrated that there was insignificant difference and therefore the null hypothesis: “There was no statistically

significant difference in the Self Esteem of urban and rural students” was failed to be rejected. Urban and rural students had comparable level of Self Esteem.

Table 8: Semester wise difference in Self Esteem

	Sum squares	Df	Mean scores	F	Sig
Between groups	64.87	20	3.244	.822	.684
Within groups	548.62	139	3.947		
Total	613.500	159			

In Table 8, the value of $F(20,139) = .822$ and significant difference $p = .684$ illustrated that there was insignificant difference and therefore the null hypothesis: “There was no statistically significant difference in the Self Esteem of students at

different semesters” was failed to be rejected. The students from various semesters were found alike in their perception of Self Esteem possessed by them.

Table 9: Program wise difference in Self Esteem

	Sum squares	Df	Mean scores	F	Sig
Between groups	8.057	20	.403	.591	.914
Within groups	94.687	139	.681		
Total	102.744	159			

In Table 9 the value of $F(20,139) = .591$ and significant difference i.e. $.914$ confirmed that there was insignificant difference and therefore the null hypothesis: “There was no statistically significant difference in the Self Esteem of students of

different programs” was failed to be rejected. The students from various programs were found indistinguishable in their perception of Self Esteem possessed by them.

Table 10: Impact of Self Esteem on Academic Achievement

Predictor	B	SE	β	t	p
Constant	2.143	.399	–	5.378	< .001
Self-esteem	.019	.018	.085	1.075	.284

Note. $R^2 = .007$, $F(1, 158) = 1.156$, $p = .284$.

In table 10, the value of $p = .284$ illustrated that there was insignificant impact of self-esteem on academic achievement and therefore the null hypothesis: “There was no statistically significant effect of Self Esteem on academic achievement” was failed to be rejected. Students’ Self Esteem had not affected their Academic Achievement

It’s a powerful factor among students particularly at higher education institutes. Current study testified that the students of any gender, locality, semester, and program had alike self-perceived level of Self Esteem which was undeniably grander. It was different from what another study titled as “Anxiety and Self Esteem among University Students: Comparison between Albania and Kosovo”, found; Self Esteem and gender had been found negatively associated (Mustafa et al., 2015).

A study titled as “Test anxiety, Self Esteem and academic performance among adolescents”

Discussion

Self Esteem is an overall assessment of one’s personal value (Orth & Robins, 2011).

showed that urban students had improved Self Esteem and admirable academic performance in contrast to their rural counterparts (Alam, 2013). Finding of better Self Esteem in present research was similar to aforementioned study but the situation was contradictory in its impact on students' academic achievement. Contrarily, in another study titled as "Self Esteem and academic performance relationship amongst the second year undergraduate students of University Kebangsaan Malaysia, Kuala Lumpur Campus", the results showed that Self Esteem is the major reason which can affect the academic performance of a person, more important than additional basic issues which include anxiety along with body image (Rosli et al., 2012).

Supporting the results of the study, it is showed that there is no association of Self Esteem and Academic Achievements was found (Naderi et al., 2009). The research revealed both of the congruous as well as incongruous results in current research project and at the same time, noted the matching phenomena in the literature.

Conclusion

The study conclusively revealed that Self Esteem was marked to be identical among male, female, urban and rural university students. In the same way, the students at all levels (semesters) and in all programs were testified to have an equivalent level of Self Esteem. The surprising conclusion of current study showed that self-esteem has no effect on academic achievement of university students. Calls into question previously established positive deterministic association of two variables, more in-depth examinations could provide a clearer understanding of the observable phenomenon.

Recommendation

The current study was restricted to a single university, which we as a researchers, believe to be the main obstacle. However, we made an effort to include a diverse sample in this, taking into account the gender, place of residence, family background, and all semesters from different study programs of students.

Therefore, it was proposed that a larger and more varied sample would provide more solid

findings and a trustworthy representation of the result.

Future researchers were advised to explore other factors to examine the association between Self Esteem and academic achievements. A better context for the findings would be provided by mediating and/or moderating the effects of many other variables. To provide a more thorough representation of the sample participants, similar research should be conducted at other universities.

The research instrument's reliability was 0.600, and it was suggested that before modifying the research instrument(s), the researchers should do item analysis for future studies.

Author's Contribution

SN conducted the analysis and drafted the manuscript. AAS, refined the manuscript and incorporated required changes subsequently. RY helped in formatting and write up. All authors contributed to the article planning, reading of draft and approved the submitted version.

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Conflict of Interest

Researchers declares no conflict of interest.

Ethics Statement

According to local legislation and institutional requirements, ethical review and approval was not required for the study on human participants. But while preparing this manuscript all other ethical considerations were fulfilled and participants consent were received.

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